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Lessons Learned from Coherent Resilience Tabletop Exercises in the Baltic Region

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Extended abstract

Current geopolitical environment in the Baltic Sea region requires continuous actions to build and enhance resilience of energy infrastructure. Tabletop Exercise proved to be an important tool that can bring together all the stakeholders and foster resilience through cooperation, sharing and networking of neighbouring states or regions. A Tabletop Exercise is a facilitated discussion-based exercise conducted in a stress-free environment. The NATO Energy Security Centre of Excellence (NATO ENSEC COE) and the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission (JRC) have jointly organised three tabletop exercises in the Baltic region addressing resilience and energy security. The exercises were conducted every two years in 2019, 2021 and 2023. All three exercises were evaluated by a team from Naval Postgraduate School (NPS). This paper presents three tabletop exercises and their major outcomes.

A tabletop exercise (TTX) is an informal, discussion-based exercise in which a team discusses their roles and responses during an emergency or crisis, considering several examples of potentially risky situations. The atmosphere is collegial and exploratory, and is not meant to put participants in the mindset they'd have during a real crisis event. Tabletop exercises are used to prepare for crises, with primary aim to identify gaps in legislation and share best practices among the participants [1].

A TTX is in particular useful tool to discuss and prepare for crisis events that might affect several countries having different legal, governance and emergency response systems that need to interact and work together in case of real event. TTX not only serves as a perfect networking event, it could also serve to spark and set up intergovernmental agreements for common crisis response.

Coherent Resilience (CORE) is a series of national and regional level tabletop exercises (TTXs) aimed at enhancing resilience of energy systems in an era of hybrid threats. CORE TTXs have been conducted in Ukraine as well as national and regional programs in the Baltic States and other countries.

The main objective of this study is to provide an overview of the three exercises completed in the Baltic Sea region in the period of 2019-2023 and evaluate their importance and effect in increasing resilience and energy security in the region. As the main focus of the exercises is to improve resilience of energy systems, resilience is understood as system's ability to withstand external shocks and continue to provide services as long as possible, see more details in [2].

Coherent Resilience 2019 (CORE 19) was a Tabletop Exercise on the Baltic States and hybrid threats related to regional natural gas supplies and critical energy infrastructure protection. The TTX took place 14-16 May 2019 in Vilnius, Lithuania. The goal of the exercise was to support the national authorities and natural gas transmission system operators (TSO) of the Baltic States in ensuring supply of gas to consumers and mitigating the disruption over the Baltic region. This three-day regional, multilateral, interagency, and public-private sector event was divided into three phases including an academic seminar, a two-day TTX, and a distinguished visitors' day that included after-action briefings. The event brought together 108 participants from 14 NATO and European Union countries, who came from 35 different organisations representing gas supply and energy security stakeholders.

The goal of the exercise was to support national authorities and gas transmission system operators of the Baltic States in ensuring supply of gas to consumers and mitigating the disruption over the Baltic region through the

execution of a tabletop exercise, where national emergency response plans and regional cooperation were exercised. Particular attention was given to the topic solidarity agreements that are required by the EU Regulation 2017/1938.

The following are examples of key conclusions that were identified by the participants:

Tabletop Exercise as a Tool. Participants noted the value of the tabletop exercise as a forum to share best practices, discuss challenges, and review national and regional plans. Having a community of interest to focus on energy security challenges can lead to improvements in resilience of supply and systems through cooperation and communications. CORE 19 participants could see a continuous cycle of annual exercises, where this event is followed organisation, interagency, national, and again a regional-level exercise.

Future Infrastructure as a Positive Change. Planned future additions to regional energy infrastructure - as identified in the scenario 2020+ – was identified as having a significant positive effect on regional and state energy security. It was very clear to the participants that additional infrastructure would significantly lower chances for solidarity request situations. Such solidarity needs are rather low even with today's infrastructure as it became evident during the exercise. Nonetheless, it was also clear that additional work is required in all areas as it is imperative to further improve resilience.

A number of key takeaways was identified by each of 4 syndicates and these are provided in the corresponding sections of the final exercise report [3].

Coherent Resilience 2021 – Baltic (CORE 21-B) was a Tabletop Exercise on the Baltic States and hybrid threats to the regional electric grid with a focus on critical energy infrastructure protection. The TTX took place 20-24 September 2021 in Vilnius, Lithuania. The aim of the exercise was to support the national authorities and electricity system operators of the Baltic States in ensuring supply of electricity to civilian and military consumers and mitigating the possible disruption in the light of hybrid threats over the Baltic region due to vulnerabilities caused by close proximity of unsafe Belarusian Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) and the process of synchronization of the Baltic States power grid with the Continental Europe grid. CORE 21-B was a five-day regional, multilateral, interagency, and public-private sector event that was executed with an academic seminar, a three-day TTX, and a distinguished visitors' day that included after-action briefings. The event brought together over 100 participants from 12 NATO and European Union countries or partner nations, who came from 35 different organizations representing electricity supply and energy security stakeholders.

A few example key takeaways and recommendations are those identified by the broader syndicate teams that consisted of facilitators, participants, and evaluators:

There is a need for increased baseload reserve generation. There is a need in the Baltic States to increase baseload generation capacity and not to rely on interconnections only. This need is particularly evident when the Baltic States operate in isolation mode creating situations with load shedding as the only available option. **Recommendation:** Analyze the feasibility of building new baseload generation capacity in the region. Feasibility is dependent on need, cost of power, and public opinion. The type of fuel can be as diverse as practically reasonable, be it nuclear, gas, hydrogen or others. Due to ongoing climate protection regulations, low or zero greenhouse gas (GHG) emission technologies should be analyzed for feasibility.

Early Multinational Cooperation during Hybrid Scenarios would improve resilience. During crisis events, the national emergency response centers combine various stakeholders from the TSO(s), cyber agencies, intelligence agencies, and others to facilitate a coordinated national and/or multinational response. But regulations have not been updated regarding the notification and declaration of incidents for all hybrid attacks. And when events and indicators did not clearly trigger declaration of a crisis event, the lines of communication to share information across states and agencies were inconsistent and would likely lead to information gaps at decision-making levels. When thresholds were not clearly exceeded, most reporting continued via internal channels, further preventing effective national and multinational response. **Recommendations:** To improve pre-crisis resiliency, establish reporting channels and procedures for TSOs to collaborate amongst themselves regarding events which do not rise to national emergency or crisis levels. Low-level, cross-agency and cross-nation information sharing will permit the Baltic states and their allies to identify potential attacks more rapidly and respond more precisely, neutralizing single aspects in isolation (where possible). The channels should be exercised during multinational exercises at ministry and TSO levels. Pre-crisis resiliency also depends on the level

of uncertainty regarding the functioning of the Belarusian NPP that was built in close proximity to the Baltic States in violation of the international nuclear and environmental safety requirements. The high level of uncertainty stemming from low safety standards and secrecy around the Belarusian NPP could motivate adversary to include a nuclear energy aspect in the hybrid attacks expecting that it will act as a strong force multiplier. In order to diminish the hybrid threat potential, the Baltic States and their allies should continue their multilateral and bilateral efforts with the aim to ensure that Belarus implements the highest international nuclear safety standards and strictly follows the principles of openness and transparency. In order to improve preparedness and response, it is important to increase awareness on how to deal with the situations when a nuclear element is used as a part of a hybrid activity toolbox.

A number of key takeaways was identified by each of 4 syndicates and these are provided in the corresponding sections of the final exercise report [4].

Coherent Resilience 2023 – Baltic (CORE 23-B) was a Tabletop Exercise on the energy system of the Baltic States with a focus on maritime critical energy infrastructure protection against hybrid threats. The Tabletop Exercise took place on 13-17 November 2023 in Riga, Latvia. The aim of the exercise was to support national authorities and key energy system stakeholders of the Baltic States and partnering nations with increasing the resiliency of their maritime energy installations and associated distribution networks in the Baltic Sea against hybrid threats. A spectrum of threats was introduced in the exercise scenario ranging from hybrid attacks and terrorism activities to conventional maritime operations. This exercise served as a collaborative venue to improve national contingency plans and procedures and develop NATO and the European Union capacity to support national authorities. CORE 23-B was a five-day regional, multilateral, interagency, and public-private sector event that was executed with an academic seminar, a three-day exercise, and a distinguished visitors' day that included after-action briefings. This report focuses largely on syndicate responses to the exercise scenario vignettes and injects to include capturing key takeaways and recommendations. The event brought together over 120 participants from 12 NATO and European Union countries or partner nations, who came from 45 different organizations representing maritime, energy supply and security stakeholders.

In the face of evolving hybrid threats to critical energy infrastructure, mechanisms for coordination, cooperation, and response between government/military/industry should also evolve across the EU. There are ambiguities and limitations in international law when it comes to classifying and responding to hybrid threats to energy systems. These ambiguities need to be addressed in part through exercises which examine specific likely threats. The broader syndicate team beyond their specific syndicates identifies the following key takeaway and recommendation of the exercise:

There is a need for increased awareness and understanding of critical energy infrastructure. There is currently no common understanding of what, exactly, constitutes critical energy infrastructure (CEI). The EU Directive defines CEI in generic way and attempts to standardize methods to identify and protect CEI are hindered by varying definitions of CEI and by individual approaches that may not be effective in a larger, collective context. While trends towards cross border energy distribution and interconnectedness are positive and do increase the resilience and redundancy of our collective energy posture, they also bring risks if countries have varying definition of what energy infrastructure is. Furthermore, there is no common practice for instituting measures to protect CEI. This most certainly leads to weak points in the collective systems, which can be exploited by an adversary to achieve exponential effects across the whole system. **Recommendation:** Formal guidelines to learn how to determine which aspects of a country or region's energy infrastructure is critical is needed, probably followed by training and modelling. In addition to assessing the infrastructure and thinking about risks, the guidelines would also instruct participants regarding what steps are needed to protect CI, with the objective of increasing security, resilience, and redundancy.

A number of key takeaways was identified by each of 4 syndicates and these are provided in the corresponding sections of the final exercise report [5].

Concluding remarks

Looking backwards, we can clearly conclude that CORE19 TTX has stimulated and actually paved the way to signatures of inter-governmental agreements on natural gas solidarity among the Baltic States. While we could

not identify such an obvious outcome from other two exercises, they clearly improved trans-national exchange on best practices, helped to identify gaps and missing procedures and proposed regional measures for further actions.

It is important to note that exercise reports – ideally – do not end exercises, for the region, nations, agencies and organizations that participated in those TTXs. They should each develop an Improvement Plan based on the relevant key takeaways identified. Each institution is to further analyse the key takeaways pertinent to them in order to identify the best means to facilitate improvements and develop the corresponding plan of action.

The participant's surveys conducted by NPS at the end of each exercise indicate the need and importance of such exercises. This need is in particular evident in this time of threats and attacks becoming more and more realistic.

We do believe that three exercises, all taking more than 6 months effort to organise and arrange, will contribute to the energy security and resilience improvements of the Baltic Sea region.

References

1. FEMA. (2019). Discussion-based Exercises – Types, Goals, and Conduct. Federal Emergency Management Agency, Department of Homeland Security. URL: <https://emilms.fema.gov/>
2. Vamanu, B., Martišauskas, L., Karagiannis, G., Masera, M., Krausmann, E., Kopustinskas, V., Development of indicator framework for critical energy infrastructure, European Commission, Ispra, 2021, JRC125802.
3. Kopustinskas, V., Šikas, R., Walzer, L., Vamanu, B., Masera, M., Vainio, J. and Petkevičius, R., Tabletop exercise: Coherent Resilience 2019 (CORE 19) - Final report, EUR 29872 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2019, ISBN 978-92-76-11830-5, doi:10.2760/356320, JRC118083.
4. Nave C., Kopustinskas V., Dirginčius E., Walzer L., Beniulytė G., Purvins A., Masera M., Nussbaum D., Norg V., Užkuraitis D. Tabletop exercise: Coherent Resilience 2021 Baltic (CORE21-B) - Final report, EUR 31020 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-49466-9, doi: 10.2760/74397, JRC128730.
5. Dirginčius, E., Kopustinskas, V., Aukščionis, D., Lynn, C.B., Užkuraitis, D., Vlagsma, K., Nussbaum, D., Trakimavičius, L., Asensio Bermejo, I., Bazukaitė, P., Foretic, H. and Babilas, P., Tabletop exercise: Coherent Resilience Baltic 2023 (CORE 23-B), Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/702667>, JRC137990.